

Thermochemistry of Solution of Salt Lakes. VI. Enthalpies of Dilution of $\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7\text{-MgSO}_4\text{-Li}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ Systems at 298.15 K

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Most of the salt lakes on the Qinghai-Xizang plateau in China belong to the seawater system with abundant boron and lithium. In the late period of evaporation, because of the deposition of most salts of sodium and potassium and of high concentrating factor for boron and lithium, the brine became actually the Li^+ , Mg^{2+} / Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ system. The phase equilibrium and properties of saturated solution in the above system have been reported¹. The enthalpies of dilution of $\text{MgB}_{2n}\text{O}_{3n+1}\text{-MgCl}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ ($n = 1, 2, 3$), $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7\text{-Li}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-LiCl-H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7\text{-MgSO}_4\text{-MgCl}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ systems have also been reported^{2,3}. Here we reports the heat of dilution, heat capacities and apparent molal enthalpies of the quaternary system $\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7\text{-MgSO}_4\text{-Li}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ at 298.15 K. The Debye-Hückel limiting law was used to extrapolate the heat of dilution in multi-component system.

Results and Discussion

The heat of dilution and heat capacities of the quaternary system $\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7\text{-MgSO}_4\text{-Li}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ were measured to cover a range from initial ionic strength I_0 to I_f at 298.15 K. The results are reported in Table 1. In Table 1, M_1 is the total molality (all solutes) of the system, C the specific heat capacity, ΔH_a the heat of dilution and ϕ_1 the apparent molal enthalpy.

The apparent molal enthalpy, $\phi_1 = -\Delta H_a(I_1 \rightarrow 0)$, was determined with the extended limiting law equation⁴,

$$\phi_1 = S_H I^{1/2} [(1 + I^{1/2})^{-1} - (\sigma/3)] + BI + CI^{3/2} \quad (1)$$

where, S_H is the Debye-Hückel limiting slope ($S_H = \omega A_H$; $\omega = (1/2)\sum v_i z_i^2$; v_i and z_i are the number and valence of ion i and $A_H = 2.8786 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ ion}^{-1/2}$ at 298.15 K),

$$\sigma = (3/I^{3/2}) [(1 + I^{1/2}) - (1 + I^{1/2})^{-1} - 2 \ln(1 + I^{1/2})] \quad (2)$$

and B and C are adjustable parameters. The values of B and C have been determined from the experimentally measured enthalpy of dilution.

$$\Delta H_a(I_1 \rightarrow I_f) = -\Delta \phi_1(I_1 \rightarrow I_f) \quad (3)$$

using

$$(\Delta \phi_L - S_H \Delta \{I^{1/2} | 1 + I^{1/2} \}^{-1} - (\sigma/3)) / \Delta I = B + C(\Delta(I^{3/2})/\Delta I) \quad (4)$$

plots of the left-side of eq. (4) vs $\Delta(I^{3/2})/\Delta I$ for the $\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7\text{-MgSO}_4\text{-Li}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ system. The result by a least-squares fit are $B = -5.82221$, $C = 4.02184$.

The apparent molal enthalpies $\phi_{1(i)}$ of $\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7\text{-MgSO}_4\text{-Li}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ systems to cover the ionic strength range from 15 to 0.1, can be calculated from equation,

$$\phi_{1(i)} = \phi_{1(f)} - \Delta H_a(I_1 - I_f) \quad (5)$$

using the heat of dilution ΔH_a and the apparent molal enthalpy $\phi_{1(f)}$ of the final ionic strength. The results are given in Table 1.

Experimental

Magnesium sulphate and lithium sulphate (both A.R. grade) were recrystallised. Magnesium tetraborate was synthesised from analytical reagents; X-ray analysis identified it as $\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The eutonic point solution of the quaternary system $\text{MgB}_4\text{O}_7\text{-MgSO}_4\text{-Li}_2\text{SO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by isothermal ($25.00 \pm 0.03^\circ$) method, the composition (mol kg^{-1}) being MgB_4O_7 , 0.08935; MgSO_4 , 2.2595; Li_2SO_4 , 1.9215.

TABLE 1—HEAT CAPACITY AND HEAT OF DILUTION AND APPARENT MOLAL ENTHALPY OF MgB_4O_7 - $MgSO_4$ - Li_2SO_4 - H_2O SYSTEM AT 298.15 K $I_o = 15.1597$

I_i	M_i mol kg ⁻¹	C kJ kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔH_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ϕ_i kJ mol ⁻¹
15.159 7	4.270 3	3.006 1	0.000 0	6.689 1
14.171 0	3.991 8	3.058 5	-0.418 4	6.270 7
13.193 7	3.716 5	3.112 6	-1.001 2	5.687 9
12.143 8	3.420 8	3.173 5	-1.544 7	5.144 4
11.398 7	3.210 9	3.218 6	-1.896 1	4.793 0
10.021 8	2.823 0	3.306 3	-2.542 6	4.236 5
9. 238 2	2.602 3	3.358 9	-2.724 0	3.965 1
8.088 8	2.278 5	3.440 0	-3.070 7	3.618 4
7.005 3	1.973 3	3.520 9	-3.420 4	3.268 7
6.025 6	1.697 3	3.598 3	-3.684 4	3.004 7
5.023 7	1.420 6	3.680 2	-3.905 2	2.783 9
4.091 4	1.152 5	3.764 0	-4.104 0	2.585 1
3.079 2	0.867 4	3.858 3	-4.306 8	2.382 3
2.028 3	0.571 3	3.962 5	-4.520 1	2.169 0
1.001 7	0.282 2	4.071 0	-4.865 9	1.823 2
0.848 2	0.238 9	4.087 9	-4.939 9	1.749 2
0.603 3	0.169 9	4.115 1	-5.059 1	1.630 0
0.400 2	0.112 7	4.138 0	-5.183 3	1.505 8
0.208 6	0.058 8	4.159 9	-5.284 8	1.404 3
0.104 2	0.029 4	4.171 9	-5.410 3	1.278 8

An LKB-87001 calorimeter and a thermostatic bath ($25.000 \pm 0.001^\circ$) were used to measure the heat of dilution and the heat capacity. The accuracy of the calorimeter was tested² by measuring the heat effect of a standard reaction of trishydroxymethylaminomethane with HCl at 298.15 K. Experimental procedures for heat of dilution and heat capacity measurements were the same as described earlier^{2,3}.

References

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